

Bidirectional Modular DC/DC Converter for HVDC battery in Aircraft Applications

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Abstract

This presentation deals with the optimal design of a modular bidirectional DC/DC converter used in More Electrical Aircrafts applications, developed at Cleansky 2 project called HYPNOTIC. The converter will make the interface between an HVDC battery and the HVDC network bus. The specific application requires bidirectional converter having high power density and also high efficiency for a wide load/source variation. Partners of HYPNOTIC project propose an approach to achieve this performance by connecting several low-power converter units in parallel and manage the power in each one. However, this performance can only be achieved if converter modularity is associated with the use of wide bandgap devices, such as SiC semiconductors. Preliminary results show that the use of high-performance semiconductors may simplify converter control strategy since it can be operated in hard-switching (HS) modulation instead of complex soft-switching (SS) modulation. This presentation also shows that there is an optimal number of small converters in parallel, which provides very high efficiency even at low power as well as high reliability.

Introduction

This presentation introduces the work being done in project HYPNOTIC, funded within Cleansky 2. The objective of this project is the design and development of a DC/DC power converter to integrate an HVDC battery into the electrical system of an airplane. This project will be integrated in the PROVEN test bench by AIRBUS in Toulouse.

There are several challenges for the integration of a battery in an airplane electrical system. In this application, bidirectional power converter is required to control the voltage, current and power between the aircraft electrical network and a storage element. Storage systems must be able to deliver a large amount of energy in a short period of time (high power), but usually they are slowly charged (low power). Thus, since the delivered energy by the battery and its charging energy are the same in a flight cycle, a power converter between battery and electrical network must have high efficiency both at high and low power.

Traditionally, battery in an aircraft electrical system plays a secondary role in energy supply, most of the times it is only used for maintenance or emergency situations. However, a well-managed battery can be used for other purposes. Batteries are excellent energy reservoirs to be used when needed. This projects also deals with this concept of energy management, to support other sources of energy at certain operation points, in addition to the traditional use of emergency and peak power energy supply.

The system considered in this paper is composed by an aircraft DC network with $\pm 270\text{Vdc}$ nominal voltage and an ion-lithium battery set with 570Vdc nominal voltage. The network differential voltage can oscillate between 500Vdc and 650Vdc in normal mode operation, reaching transiently 900V in case of failure. Battery voltage vary from 300V to 650V , depending on

its charge level. Nominal power is 40kW in source mode and 5kW in charging mode. In addition, other requirements and standards should be satisfied:

- Global converter efficiency greater than 99% at high and low power (source and charging mode);
- Total converter weight (power stage) lower than 10kg ;
- Airbus HVDC Power Quality Standard (0 – 150kHz);
- Conducted Emissions DO-160 Standard (150kHz – 152MHz) - Category L.

The design work is currently ongoing, although partial results will be presented in this More Electrical Aircraft Congress, with particular focus on the design considerations and innovations, which are summarized in the following sections.

Design Approach

Several design considerations have been taken into account for the design of this converter. In [1], a more detailed description of these considerations is described. In this section, a brief description of the most relevant ones is presented.

Many DC/DC non-isolated topologies have been considered. Finally, the topology in Figure 1 have been selected because it is bi-directional can be used in soft and hard switching and provides high voltage variation in both sides.

Once the topology is selected, the first design consideration is the ability to perform with high efficiency in a wide operating range. The converter operational concept requires to operate for short periods at full power while operating in a variable power below nominal power for long periods. It is particularly difficult to achieve high efficiency with a single converter supposed to work at high and low power. At high power, the converter requires power semiconductor with low on-state resistance (R_{DSon}). However, low R_{DSon} implies in components with high

Figure 1: Complete single module of the Bidirectional Buck + Boost Cascade, including filters

parasitic capacitances, which present high switching losses. These switching losses result in low efficiency at low power operation point. In order to achieve high efficiency, a modular approach has been chosen.

Figure 2: Efficiency profile of modular converters in parallel

Fig. 2 shows some efficiency profiles as a function of the output power, considering a modular converter with nominal power 40kW, divided in six 6.7kW modules in parallel. The variable N_{on} is the number of enabled modules, which can vary from one to six. The black curve also in Fig. 2 is the overall efficiency profile if N_{on} is controlled as a function of the output power. Thus, high efficiency even at low power is achieved.

In addition, the use of Silicon Carbide MOSFETs simplifies the discussion of Hard switching vs soft Switching techniques. This topology allows the use of soft switching by using the four transistors in switching period, while only two are needed in hard switching strategy. Considering the inductor current indicated in Figure 3 for both switching strategies, the estimated losses in case of Soft switching is 54.3W while in Hard switching only 45.3W, at 40kHz switching frequency. Furthermore, a considerable control effort and a suitable hardware to detect zero voltage are needed to implement Soft Switching mode. For all these reasons, soft-switching will not be used in this design.

Roadmap

Currently, a detailed mock-up of this inverter is being designed to be tested in the following months. A strong collaboration between all the partners (Skylife

Engineering, IRT Saint-Exupery, Aeromechs and University of Campania) and the Topic Manager (Airbus DS) in the project will allow to achieve final test equipment, expected for October 2022. In Figure 4, a model of the front view is presented.

Figure 3: (a) Inductor current in hard-switching mode; (b) Inductor current in soft switching mode

Figure 4: Front view

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References

[1] Sathler et al., "Optimization of Bidirectional Modular DC/DC Converter for Low and High Power Operation in Aircraft Applications," 22nd IEEE International Conference on Industrial Technology (ICIT), 2021, pp. 458-463, doi: 10.1109/ICIT46573.2021.945351